

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AND OTHER FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article discusses the methods of teaching English and other foreign languages, modern technologies used in teaching English, and popularization of English among young people.

Key words: Multimedia, English language, pedagogue, teaching methodology, foreign language popularization, modern methods, pedagogy, best practice.

Introduction.

On May 19, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, aimed at increasing the quality and scope of teaching foreign languages, including English, "On measures to bring the popularization of foreign language learning to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan " decision was made. In order to coordinate work in this regard, the Agency for Popularization of Foreign Language Learning was established under the Cabinet of Ministers. Although the agency has not yet started its activities, effective and systematic work is being done to popularize the study of foreign languages. Applying advanced experiences and achievements of pedagogy to education is one of the important conditions of today. Currently, a huge experience base has been formed, which the teacher can use during his work, and it is getting richer every day. But still, it is difficult for teachers and future professionals to master these experiences. The teacher's role in creating best practice and popularizing it among colleagues is of particular importance. Educators should consider the cost and effectiveness of new pedagogical practices. The orientation of the teacher's practical activity to innovation allows the practical application of the achievements achieved as a result of theoretical pedagogical research. In order to popularize the results of such studies, it is necessary to introduce them to the general public. Such news can be delivered to representatives of other pedagogies by giving quick advice by experts in the field, conducting trainings at special seminars, lecturing at conferences, giving a series of lectures to future pedagogues.

Today, students and young people pay attention to his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose the methods and forms of organizing educational activities that best meet the stated goal of personal development of students. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been raised more and more. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practice a foreign language.

Popular methods of teaching and learning English, Internet resources were used in the research process. In the process of writing the article, theoretical-deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, principles of logic were used. The task of the teacher is to create

conditions for the practical acquisition of the language by each student, to allow each student to show his activity and creativity. is the choice of educational methods. The task of the teacher is to activate the student's knowledge activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative teaching, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, to individualize teaching taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning and mastery. will help. ensures differentiation. Forms of working with computer educational programs in foreign language classes include: vocabulary learning; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical phenomena. The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to get any information: regional geographical materials, youth life news, articles in newspapers and magazines, etc. can be solved: the ability to build reading skills and use global network materials; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work is aimed at studying the possibilities of Internet technologies for expanding the worldview of schoolchildren, establishing and maintaining business relations and relations with their peers in English-speaking countries. Students participate in online tests, quizzes, contests, olympiads, correspond with their peers in other countries, chat, videoconference, etc.

Students can learn about a problem they are currently working on in a project. The machine can be "friendly" with the user and sometimes "support" him, but he will never show signs of anger and will not let you get bored. In this sense, the use of computers can be most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, upbringing, development) are realized in the process of realizing this main goal. The communicative approach includes the formation of communication skills and intercultural communication skills, which are the basis of Internet activities. Without communication, the Internet has no meaning - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - this is the number and size of participants. this. the biggest conversation. By participating in a foreign language class, we will create a real communication model for him. Currently, communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural context, autonomy and humanism of education are of priority. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach the ability to navigate freely in a foreign language environment and respond appropriately to different situations, that is, communication. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop appropriate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies, especially the Internet, are trying to correct this error. Communicative approach is a strategy simulating communication aimed at conscious understanding of the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. A communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not

only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that makes it possible to distinguish this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their own thoughts. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its purpose is to make students interested in learning foreign language by gathering and expanding knowledge and experience. One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is interaction in the lesson. is to create a mystery that is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and completing communicative goals and resulting actions through the medium of speech." By teaching real language, the Internet helps to develop speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest and therefore effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond appropriately to them in a foreign language. One of the technologies that provide student-centered education is the project method, which is a method of developing creativity, knowledge activity, and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprosjekt, collective, oral, concrete, written and internet projects. In actual practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informational features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. I believe that project-based education teaches children to cooperate, and cooperative learning instills moral values such as mutual aid and empathy, develops creativity, and activates students. In general, in the process of teaching the project, teaching and learning are inseparable. The project method develops students' communication skills, behavioral culture, the ability to form ideas briefly and easily, the ability to tolerate the opinions of communication partners, the ability to obtain information from various sources, processes using modern computer technologies, and creates a language environment. helps the emergence of natural needs. in foreign language communication.

Summary:

The form of project work is one of the most relevant technologies that allow students to apply the accumulated knowledge on the subject. Students expand their worldview, the limits of knowledge of the language, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, understand each other when defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computers, and thus create the possibility of direct contact with the real language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom only with the help of textbooks. Working on a project is a creative process. The student searches for a solution to the problem independently or under the guidance of the teacher, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of scientific knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual abilities. In the process of learning foreign languages, the project method can be used as part of the program materials on almost any subject. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities. Modern technologies also use collaborative technology. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in different educational settings. Children are put into groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task, in which everyone's role is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the

whole group. That's why weak students try to find out what they don't understand from weak ones, and strong students try to understand the task thoroughly. And the whole class benefits because the gaps are closed together. The introduction of information technologies into education greatly diversifies the process of information perception and processing. Thanks to the computer, the Internet and multimedia, a unique opportunity has been created for students to master a large amount of data with further analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity is also expanding significantly. In the context of using multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, have conversations and hold teleconferences.

References:

- 1.Aitchison, J. (1972) General Linguistics, English Universities Press.
- 2.Aitchison, J. (1978) Linguistics, Hodder & Stoughton, 2nd edn.
- 3.Jalolov J.J, Maxkamova S.T, Ashurov Sh.S "English language teaching methodology" Tashkent-2015 " Fan va texnologiya "publishing.
- 4.Matmurotov Z "The using of role-playing in teaching foreign languages" Молодой учёный N24 июнь 2017.
- 5.Shaxodat Pardayeva, Gulnoz Murotiva, Nazira Isanova "The current state of teaching foreign languages".